

Analysis of Talent Management on Corporate Sustainability of Start-Up Company (Case Study at PT. Farmalab Indoutama)

Ristya Widyasari¹
Postgraduate Master's in Management
Mercu Buana University
Jakarta, Indonesia

Lenny Christina Nawangsari²
Postgraduate Master's in Management
Mercu Buana University
Jakarta, Indonesia

Abstract:- In fulfilling the needs of human resources in this competent company, the company must seriously process it to meet the successor goals for future business continuity (corporate sustainability). Currently, human resource management has entered a new stage, the emergence of the term talent management against the background of a recurring company problem, namely companies that go all out to attract employees' energy to join the company, but only spend less time using and managing their talents. This research discusses how companies can implement talent management in supporting corporate sustainability. By using qualitative methods and data analysis processes using Nvivo 12, the final result of this study is to find a model concept on effective implementation in the implementation of talent management so as to support corporate sustainability in the company PT Farmalab Indoutama.

Keywords:- Talent Management, Corporate Sustainability, Model Concept.

I. INTRODUCTION

In fulfilling the needs of human resources in this competent company, it must be seriously processed by the company to meet the successor goals for future business continuity. The achievement of a company is in managing human resources effectively and efficiently with the aim of achieving a company's goals, as well as having sustainable organizational performance in business.

The growth and success of any business relies heavily on having the right people with the right skills in the right position. Employees in this category are talented employees who are seen as the most important human resources leading to competitive advantage as a form of maintaining corporate sustainability [1].

PT Farmalab Indoutama (FLIU) which is a subsidiary of PT Indofarma, Tbk which is a member of the Pharmaceutical BUMN Holding engaged in health services. In its development, FLIU underwent commercial development in accordance with the articles of association and commercial permits. Creating a sustainable company in terms of business development. FLIU formulates important questions related to the impact on social, economic and environmental aspects

approaching the achievement of the company's sustainable goals, namely contribution to global development and the achievement of sustainable goals. The following is the phenomenon of optimizing corporate sustainability from 3 aspects, namely economic, social, environmental aspects.

Based on the phenomenon of optimizing corporate sustainability above, it makes companies aware of the importance of competent and committed human resources in order to prioritize the fulfillment of sustainability aspects in the economic, social, and environmental fields optimally and consistently. Based on company data obtained from brief interviews with several employees in the last 3 years related to the process of talent management implemented by PT Farmalab Indoutama, the results show that the problems that occur regarding talent management are not effective so that they affect the development and corporate sustainability.

Based on the results of interviews with several Division Managers at FLIU companies, it can be concluded that there are several problems that occur regarding ineffective talent management that affect the development and corporate sustainability in FLIU, namely.

- At the initial stage in the recruitment process, it is not selective in checking background checking, does not place employees according to business needs, does not go through the psychological stage of testing for new employees so that they cannot see a picture of a person's mental health condition, a person's personality while working even in the face of pressure at work and there is no health test for new employees.
- Not doing on-boarding which is part of the process for adjusting new employees to their new place of work so as not to create engagement between employees and the company.
- Lack of training & development programs as a form to increase productivity, quality of work, and reduce job risks in order to maintain the company's business sustainable strategy.
- There is no performance appraisal for existing employees so there is no measuring medium to determine promotion and in increasing employee productivity there is no feedback or feedback for outstanding employees.
- There is no retaining program activity in the employee retaining program so that employees are less loyal to the

company and there are the best employees choosing to resign.

Previous research still discusses Organizational Culture, Green Human Resource Management, Intellectual Capital, Green Transformational Leadership on corporate sustainability and the effects of talent management, knowledge management and work culture with organizational performance using quantitative methods, while this study will examine Talent Management on Corporate Sustainability using qualitative methods.

Based on this, this research is interested in finding answers to several phenomena, previous research and problems that arise in FLIU companies in relation to corporate sustainability. This research will also focus on finding out what factors determine the implementation of integrated talent management so as to find a form of concept design that can support corporate sustainability and to get and retain the best employees.

II. LITERATURE

A. Corporate Sustainability

Corporate Sustainability is a business approach taken by the company through the results of the performance of employees working in the company so that it can create the interests of consumers and stakeholders in the long term [2]. The direct and indirect interests of the organization such as shareholders, employees, clients, society and others, without compromising its ability to meet the needs of future stakeholders. Corporate sustainability is transformed into organizational work practices in Indonesia's hospitality sector, where waste generation and water and energy consumption are the main environmental obligations [3]. Corporate Sustainability used in this study are some of the following dimensions [4].

- Economic : Refers to the performance indicators of employees in a company to reduce input costs with the same level of output, such performance can work with government officials to protect the interests of the company.
- Social : Includes performance indicators of employees in a company to improve health and safety, act on the need to fund local community initiatives, protect the claims and rights of indigenous peoples or local communities, show concern for the visual aspects of facilities and operations, communicate the company's environmental impacts and risks to the general public and consider stakeholders in investment decisions with formal dialogue.
- Environment : Includes indicators of employee performance indicators in an enterprise to reduce energy consumption, reduce waste and emissions from operations, reduce the use of traditional fuels by replacing some non-polluting energy sources, carry out voluntary actions for environmental restoration, conduct environmental audit actions, public disclosure, employee training and immunity.

B. Talent Management

Talents are employees of an organization or company that can contribute above average through good performance and have potential that can affect the development of the organization. Its development is short-term and long-term. Relevant talent is at the level applicable to all functions and groups of organizations or companies [5].

Talent management can exist because of this phenomenon, and witness the development of existing military talents. In many companies it is estimated that due to increasingly fierce competition and a limited number of candidates, many organizations find it difficult to maintain the best resources, as well as difficulties in recruiting potential and highly qualified prospective employees.

In general, there are 3 (three) main benefits of having and implementing a talent management process in an organization [6].

- Good talent management results support the competitiveness of the organization
- There is certainty about the availability of qualified talent or human resources necessary to carry out the core functions of the organization
- Good talent management creates a good public perception of reputable organizations while encouraging members of the organization to stick with the organization.

Talent management has 3 (three) dimensions, namely [6].

- Recruitment: the process of finding and selecting suitable employees to perform the necessary tasks in the company. The indicator is the recruitment and orientation process
- Retain: processes aimed at retaining talented employees in the company. The metrics are the performance management process and the recognition process.
- Developing: A process aimed at developing employee skills to improve capabilities and efficiency. The indicator is the process of training and the opportunity to improve skills

There is an influence of Organizational Culture on Corporate Sustainability [7]. In addition, there is a positive influence of Green Human Resource Management on Corporate Sustainability [8]. Other research states that there is an influence of Intellectual Capital on Corporate Sustainability [9]. There is also a positive influence of Green Transformational Leadership on Corporate Sustainability [10]. Furthermore, there are studies that state that talent management, knowledge management and work culture together have a significant effect on organizational performance [11].

In addition to the research above, there are other studies that state that talent management has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Weaknesses in data analysis are less in-depth and focus on explaining the entire variable [12]. There is employee development positively influenced by the company's leadership style, and talent management is positively influenced by the company's approach to managing its workforce [13].

In other research, strategic decision-making by start-up entrepreneurs can lead to the sustainability and scalability of start-ups that contribute to the country's economy [14]. Other studies have shown that the issue of human resource management and talent management is influenced, especially the importance of motivation to retain talent from a small startup company [15]. In addition, the level of awareness of start-ups is still low in talent management. As a result, start-ups are usually unable to keep up or survive for months or years, leading to major economic and social problems in the long run [16].

The techniques used in this study are non-probability sampling techniques, namely snowball sampling (can be one company) and Purposive sampling (determining sampling not randomly with certain considerations). This is because the researcher took 5 (five) participants with certain conditions to obtain data. Data collection techniques are divided into three ways, namely interviews, observations, and document analysis.

III. RESEARCH AND METHODS

The research design in this study is qualitative with a case study approach. This case study studies the interaction between variables with each other. In the end, this research aims to implement talent management in supporting corporate sustainability in PT. Pharmalab Indoutama.

For data processing, researchers use a software application called Nvivo 12 Plus for windows. Nvivo is a software package that works extensively in the same way as Microsoft Office, where it was developed specifically for qualitative data analysis. From the results of the above exposure, the thought framework used in this study is succinctly as follows:

Fig 1 : Conceptual Framework

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This research was conducted for the first time by conducting interviews with 5 respondents alternately in accordance with the interview protocol at the PT Farmalab Indoutama Office. Researchers also made observations and observations related to the implementation of talent management that has been running. After conducting interviews and collecting interview data, researchers analyzed the correlation relationships of informants' answers to see their degree of linearity. If you get an answer that is outside.

The result of drawing data to see the similarity and relationship of the source's answers as shown above. It can be seen that the Pearson coefficient value from the results obtained in the Nvivo 12 Software has a value of > 0.68 (Strong) which means that the researcher states that all informant answers will be used as a further analysis process because they have the same level of linearity and focus as this study, so that no answers from informants are discarded.

The next step taken in the analysis is the researcher by comparing the answers between informants on each question asked as a form of triangulation of significant others. Then next, based on the informant's answer, the researcher makes the main keyword from the informant's answer to get a conclusion in the similarity of the answer from the phenomenon he wants to know by taking the most answers from the informant to draw conclusions by the researcher.

Based on the search results with the Word Frequency Query feature in NVivo 12 from various data sources that have been imported, the word company is the top 5 words with the most frequency, namely the words training (0.83%), boarding (0.66%), corporate (0.56%), recruitment (0.53%), sustainability (0.53%), from all data obtained in the interview process of respondents in this study. The following image shows the search results of the most frequently discussed words during the interview session.

To find out the most frequently spoken or discussed words in research interview sessions, researchers used the word cloud present in Nvivo 12. The following figure shows the Word Cloud of the 20 (twenty) most dominant words used in this research data source.

Fig 2 : Word Cloud 20 Most Dominant Words

MANAGERIAL IMPLICATIONS

A. Implementation of Talent Management at PT. Farmalab Indoutama

In the implementation of Talent Management that has been carried out at Farmalab, it still has to be improved in accordance with the stages that should be. This is proven by the results of analytical tests on the Nvivo 12 software application, where for each research variable obtained a linkage in the relationship from the word tree. The form that has been carried out at Farmalab in the talent management stage, namely

- For the recruitment process, just an interview from HR and users, salary negotiations and then sign the contract
- Absence of implementation of on boarding when new employees enter the company
- The training & development that has been carried out for Farmalab employees has not been fully fulfilled and optimal, 4) There is no retaining program for employees who have the best contribution and competence to the company.

Therefore, in talent management there needs to be 4 stages that can be implemented on Farmalab, namely

- recruitment process, in this process there is a CV review, background checking, HR & user interviews, psychological tests & health
- implementation of on boarding for new employees in the introduction (company profile, vision and mission and company culture)
- training and development, the existence of training needs analysis, program development, evaluation of the effectiveness of training as a form of providing training, coaching and development to employees
- Retaining, the provision of rewards and compensation packages where in retaining the best employees the company must have the program.

Therefore, if that stage can be implemented, then the company can find the best talent to be able to assist the company in achieving its goals and compete competitively with the company globally and internationally.

B. The Main Causes of Talent Management Implementation Have not Been Maximized in Supporting Corporate Sustainability of PT Farmalab Indoutama

From the results of data analysis, it was obtained that the main causes of talent management implementation that have not been maximized, namely:

- In the implementation of talent management that is not in accordance with the stages should be such as from the recruitment process, on boarding, training & development, and retaining. This is evidenced from the speaker's answer regarding the implementation of the stages of the recruitment process, on boarding, training & development, and retaining that there are not all stages in getting the best talent for the company and a statement from the top management of Farmalab who only recruits with the interview stage and selects talents who already have specific certified skills due to the Farmalab business line which is a health service such as Antigen Swab, PCR and laboratories require talents who have special and specific skills.
- In the implementation of corporate sustainability which consists of 3 aspects, namely economic, environmental and social, it is still in the adjustment stage and there needs to be repeated warnings for employees. This is evidenced from the speaker's answer regarding the implementation of corporate sustainability which consists of these 3 aspects, namely the economic aspect where Farmalab gets benefits, the environmental aspect where Farmalab employees still do not care about the efficient use of the environment around the office such as water, electricity and for social aspects where Farmalab is still in the stage of branding a company in creating company brand awareness by following all programs that organized by the State-Owned Pharmaceutical Holding and participating in CSR (Corporate Social Responsibility) carried out by the parent company, Biofarma. Where Farmalab is a subsidiary of one of the Pharmaceutical Holdings, namely Indofarma.

C. Model Concept on The Effectiveness of Talent Management on Corporate Sustainability of PT Farmalab Indoutama

Based on the answer data from the respondents in the interview session, it shows the role of top management which shows that the concept of a suitable model related to talent management that can be implemented effectively in the company. This conclusion was drawn by the researcher based on the answer from the informant to question P-3.2, namely the need for improvement for talent management where the appropriate stages such as the recruitment process, on boarding, training & development and retaining in obtaining the best talent. In improving talent management at Farmalab, it is also adjusted to the culture and vision and mission of the company.

Thus, with talent management that is in accordance with the stages and gets the best talent, it can support the company's corporate sustainability. Finally, based on the results of the analysis above, the researcher draws the conclusion that the concept of a talent management model that can be applied to companies.

Fig 3 : Model Concept of an Effective Talent Management in Supporting Corporate Sustainability

Related to talent management that is implemented in supporting corporate sustainability and can help achieve company goals. As for what can be implemented by Farmalab, including 4 stages, namely

- recruitment process, in this process there is a CV review, background checking, HR & user interviews, psychological tests & health
- implementation of on boarding for new employees in the introduction (company profile, vision and mission and company culture)
- training and development, the existence of training needs analysis, program development, evaluation of the effectiveness of training as a form of providing training, coaching and development to employees
- Retaining, the provision of rewards and compensation packages where in retaining the best employees the company must have the program.

This is in line with previous research that states that talent management affects company performance [11]. In addition, other studies state that there is an influence of Organizational Culture on Corporate Sustainability. The two studies, aligned and supportive in this study [7]. Where related to talent management is considered influential and effective optimally in obtaining the best talent so as to improve performance in the company. Furthermore, for corporate culture in supporting corporate sustainability, it is very influential for business continuity in achieving company goals.

V. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

The results showed that related to Talent Management, top management needs to consider and provide policies to implement talent management in accordance with the stages and adjusted to the vision and mission and company culture. Related to Corporate Sustainability, top management can consider and provide creative ideas and contribute to the implementation in supporting corporate sustainability with 3 (three) aspects, namely economic, environmental, social in running more optimally.

For the top management to always evaluate the implementation of talent management in accordance with the business strategic plan or not. In addition, it is important for the HR division to look back at the company's strategic plan as an achievement of the company's targets that have been set by adjusting to the vision and mission and company culture. Furthermore, for Farmalab employees, as policy recipients and feel the benefits, and implementers can understand the implementation of talent management and the 3 (three) aspects in corporate sustainability so that they can take action and carry out all work. Further research can dig deeper and wider in proving the concept of the model presented in this study.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Aina, Riham Al & Atan, Tarik. "The Impact Of Implementing Talent Management Practices On Sustainable Organizational Performance". *Sustainability Journal*, 12, 8372, 2020
- [2]. Akhtar, N et al. "Factors in the cross-cultural Adaptation". *Journal of Research in International Education*. Vol. 14(2) 98–113, 2015
- [3]. Bombiak, E., & Marciniuk-Kluska, A. "Green human resource management as a tool for the sustainable development of enterprises: Polish young company experience". *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 10(6), 2018
- [4]. Pusat Kajian dan Pendidikan dan Pelatihan Aparatur I Lembaga Administrasi Negara. "Kajian Model Talent Management Bagi Pengembangan Karier Pegawai Negeri Sipil: Studi Pada Lembaga Administrasi Negara, PKP2A I LAN". *Research*, 6(1), 158-163, 2016
- [5]. Pella, Darmin A & Inayati, Afifah. "Talent Management (Mengembangkan SDM untuk Mencapai Pertumbuhan dan Kinerja Prima)". Jakarta: PT. Gramedia Pustaka Utama, 2011
- [6]. Capelli, Peter. "Talent on Demand. United States of America : Harvard Business School Publishing". Variables in PT. Jaya Maritime Services. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 2009
- [7]. Pratiwi, L. A., & Nawangsari, L. C. "Organizational Citizenship Behavior while Performance". *European Journal of Business and Management Research*, 6(1), 225-231, 2021
- [8]. Erfina Tri Wulandari dan Lenny Christina Nawangsari. "The Effect of Green Human Resources Management on Green corporate sustainability Companies (Case Study on Employee Claim Department PT. Prudential Life Assurance)". *European Journal of Business and Management Research*, 6(1), 238-242, 2021
- [9]. Hilman Najib, Lenny Christina Nawangsari. "Effect of Intellectual Capital Organizational Sustainability with Employee Innovative Behavior as Intervening Variables in PT. Jaya Maritime Services". *European Journal of Business and Management Research*, 6(1), 158-163, 2021
- [10]. Dymas Widisatria and Lenny Christina Nawangsari. "The Influence of Green Transformational Leadership and Motivation to Sustainable Corporate Performance with Organizational Citizenship Behavior for the Environment as a Mediating: Case Study at PT Karya Mandiri Sukses Sentosa". *European Journal of Business and Management Research*, 2021
- [11]. Dian Amrainy and Lenny Christina Nawangsari. "The Effect of Talent Management, Knowledge Management and Work Culture on the Performance in the Survey Unit Centre of Hydrography and Oceanography Indonesia Naval (Pushidrosal)". *European Journal of Business and Management Research*, 6, 23-29, 2021
- [12]. Widianingsih, N. K. N., & Wulansari, P. "Pengaruh Talent Management Terhadap Meningkatnya Kinerja Karyawan (Studi Kasus pada Wilayah Telkom Bandung)". *E-Proceeding of Management*, 5(2), 2018
- [13]. Kaok, M., Yusuf, R. M., & Dewi, A. R. S. "Pengaruh gaya kepemimpinan dan talent management terhadap pengembangan karyawan pada PT. Marsyavin Jaya Kabupaten Merauke". *Hasanuddin Journal of Applied Business and Entrepreneurship*, 2(1), 2019
- [14]. Joshi, D. "The Role of Entrepreneurs during the Growth Phase of Internet Startups in India". *Abhigyan*, 38(3), 2020
- [15]. Kumar, J., Gupta, A., Tapar, A. V., & Khan, M. C. R. "EXOS: does the retention of salesforce matter in entrepreneurial start-ups?" *Emerald Emerging Markets Case Studies*, 10(3), 2020
- [16]. Stefko, R., Fedorko, R., Svetozarovová, N., & Nastišin, L. "Start-up management and the relationship between the level of awareness among potential young entrepreneurs and the motivation to start own business". *Quality - Access to Success*, 22(183), 2021.